

ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR PREDICTION OF MICROBUCKLING INITIATION IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: In order to model the initiation of failure modes arising from static compression loading of multidirectional composites, namely kinking and free-edge delamination, we have developed a theory that predicts analytically the interlaminar shear stresses τ_{zx} and τ_{zy} . We then incorporate these shear stresses into a model of the influence of adjacent angled plies on the microbuckling and kinking of fibers in 0° plies. This leads to a general prediction of the compressive failure strains of multidirectional composite laminates. Experimental verification is described, which uses an AS4/PPS thermoplastic composite with the generic layup $[\theta/-\theta/0_2/\theta/-\theta/0]_s$ with θ varying between 10° and 90° . The theory is in good qualitative and quantitative agreement with experimental results, and explains the order of occurrence of the various failure modes.

KEYWORDS: microbuckling, kinking, interlaminar stresses, free-edge stresses, compression, laminates, modeling

INTRODUCTION

It is well-known that in-plane kinking, starting at the sample edges, is the primary failure mode of unidirectional high fiber volume fraction composites, and the initial failure mode of multidirectional composites [1-10]. To our knowledge, only five attempts have been made to model the compression behavior of non-unidirectional composites: cross-ply [11], angle-ply [12], and multidirectional composites [13-15]. None of these consider free-edge stresses. We contend that these stresses play a major role in the in-plane kinking of 0° fibers since experiments show that in-plane kinking starts at the edges [8], [16-18]. (Out-of-plane microbuckling can also occur depending on lateral constraints [19] and in cross-ply laminates [20]). We assume that for unnotched laminates, the failure of a 0° ply triggers failure in the remaining plies, especially for laminates containing significant percentages of 0° plies (note 43% of 0° plies in our experiments). Previous work [17] suggested an influence of the angle θ if plies adjacent to the 0° plies on the microbuckling strain of the latter. Among the interlaminar stresses σ_z , τ_{zx} and τ_{zy} , only the shear stresses could have an influence on the in-plane movement of the 0° fibers. This is a reasonable assumption because σ_z is normal to the movement of the 0° fibers when they buckle in-plane and should not affect their in-plane motion. FEA studies on composites show that interlaminar stresses are zero in the central portion of the specimen and become significant only in a thin boundary layer near the edges where they display exponential behavior [21-24]. Calculation of these interlaminar stresses for any layup is required. We shall then incorporate these stresses into a general microbuckling equation for a 0° fiber located at the edge of a 0° ply. A criterion governing

fiber failure is described and compared to other possible failure mechanisms, such as matrix or interlaminar failures. This enables the observed failure strains to be related to the predicted failure modes.

THEORY

Interlaminar Edge Stresses

It is seen that we need to calculate analytically the interlaminar stresses, especially their magnitude at the free edges. This is not readily done with FEA due to mesh sensitivity [24]. The work of Puppo and Evensen [25] suggests a useful approach, although their original theory applied only to a 4-layer symmetrical laminate in tension. Extension to an arbitrary number of layers requires modification of the equilibrium equations. We adopt the equivalent ply construction of [25]. A ply is replaced by a central anisotropic layer surrounded by layers of the matrix material. The thickness e of the latter is estimated from microscopy to be on the order of a fiber diameter. These matrix layers carry the interlaminar stresses. We consider a symmetrical laminate of $2N$ plies. A given ply k ($1 \leq k < N$) has a thickness h_k and its fibers make an angle θ_k with the loading direction x . The width direction is y and the thickness direction is z . The plate has a width W and a length L . Modification of the equilibrium equations of [25] is described in detail in [27]. The initial solution is made for the case of an infinitely wide laminate under uniform compression. We then superimpose the solution for a laminate under no compression but subjected to normal (p_k) and shear stresses (t_k) at the edges (based on stresses at $y = \pm W/2$ and the new boundary conditions). Displacement solutions of the form $u_k(y) = A \cdot e^{\rho y}$ are chosen since the solution is independent of x . The final expressions for the interlaminar shear stresses have the form [27]:

$$\begin{cases} \tau_{zx}^{(k)}(y, u_a) = \frac{G_m}{2e} \sum_{i=1}^{2N-2} A_i^{(1)} \cdot (\text{Fac}A_i^{(k)} - \text{Fac}A_i^{(k+1)}) \sinh(\sqrt{\rho_i} y) \\ \tau_{zy}^{(k)}(y, u_a) = \frac{G_m}{2e} \sum_{i=1}^{2N-2} A_i^{(1)} \cdot (\text{Fac}B_i^{(k)} - \text{Fac}A_i^{(k+1)}) \sinh(\sqrt{\rho_i} y) \end{cases} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq k \leq N-1 \quad (1)$$

where G_m is the matrix shear modulus, at an interface (k) between plies (k) and ($k+1$). The coefficients $\{A_i^{(1)}\}_{1 \leq i \leq 2N-2}$ are a linear function of the applied displacement u_a . Laminates that contain only 0° and 90° plies have to be treated separately due to the decoupling of the equilibrium equations. In this case [27]:

$$\begin{cases} \tau_{zx}^{(k)}(y, u_a) \equiv 0 \\ \tau_{zy}^{(k)}(y, u_a) = \frac{G_m}{2e} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} B_i^{(1)} \cdot (\text{Fac}B_i^{(k)} - \text{Fac}B_i^{(k+1)}) \sinh(\sqrt{\rho_{i+N-1}} y) \end{cases} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq k \leq N-1 \quad (2)$$

The coefficients $\{B_i^{(1)}\}_{1 \leq i \leq N-1}$ are a linear function of the applied displacement u_a .

Microbuckling of 0° Fibers

The next step is to incorporate the action of the adjacent angled plies (by means of interlaminar shear stresses) on the 0° plies and derive a general microbuckling equation for the 0° fibers. We consider general buckling for a beam on foundation. Both the fiber and the foundation are modeled as linear elastic isotropic materials. The medium surrounding the fiber may act on it in three ways: ① through a distributed couple m , ② through a distributed axial force p in the fiber direction, ③ through a distributed transverse force q normal to the fiber. It is assumed that the fiber has (before loading) the shape of a sine function $v_0(x)$ of amplitude V_0 and wavelength λ_0 . Assuming small deflections $v(x)$, we obtain the fiber equilibrium equation:

$$E_f I \frac{d^4(v - v_0)}{dx^4} + q + \frac{dm}{dx} + P \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where P is the loading force, E_f the fiber stiffness and I its moment of inertia. The next step consists in assessing the quantities m and q . Since fibers deform in the shear mode, we have:

$$m = -A_f G \frac{d(v - v_0)}{dx} = -A_f \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f} \frac{d(v - v_0)}{dx} \quad (4)$$

where A_f is the fiber cross-section area and V_f the fiber volume fraction. Now interlaminar shear stresses τ_{zy} will develop at the interface between a 0° ply and an adjacent angled-ply, in the interlaminar matrix region of thickness $2e$. They will tend to push the fiber along the y direction. Because τ_{zy} varies with y , the half of the fibers closest to the edge will be submitted to a distributed force different from the one experienced by the half of the fiber further away from the edge. The normal force q on the fiber has therefore a magnitude:

$$2r_f \left\{ \tau_{zy} \left(y = \frac{Wi}{2} \right) - \tau_{zy} \left(y = \frac{Wi}{2} - 2v \right) \right\} \approx 2r_f \left\{ \left[\frac{d\tau_{zy}}{dy} \right]_{\frac{Wi}{2}} \right\} \cdot 2v \quad (5)$$

The microbuckling equation (3) becomes therefore:

$$E_f I \frac{d^4(v - v_0)}{dx^4} - 2 \left(2r_f \right) \left[\frac{d\tau_{zy}}{dy} \right]_{\frac{Wi}{2}} v - A_f \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f} \frac{d^2(v - v_0)}{dx^2} + \frac{A_f}{V_f} |\sigma_{0^\circ \text{ply}}| \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} = 0 \quad (6)$$

As a first approximation, we may consider that the shear stress τ_{zx} has no significant effect on the microbuckling of 0° fibers. Indeed, this stress is uniformly distributed on the fiber but in the loading direction, so its effect cancels out globally.

The solution to the homogeneous differential equation (6) is sinusoidal. Solving for the amplitude V and taking into account the edge position of the fibers, we obtain:

$$V(u_a, \theta_k) = \frac{V_0}{\frac{A_f}{V_f} |\sigma_{0^\circ \text{ply}}(u_a)| + 2(2r_f) \cdot \left[\frac{d\tau_{zy}(u_a, \theta_k)}{dy} \right]_{\frac{W_i}{2}} \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\pi} \right)^2} \quad (7)$$

$$1 - \frac{E_f I \left(\frac{\pi}{\lambda_0} \right)^2 + (0.6) A_f \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f}}{}$$

Fiber failure

Failure will occur when the tensile strain in the fiber ϵ_f reaches the fiber failure strain in tension ϵ_{tf} . The maximum tensile strain in the fiber occurs at the fiber surface. The criterion for fiber failure is:

$$\epsilon_f = -\frac{|\sigma_{0^\circ \text{ply}}|}{V_f E_f} + r_f \left(\frac{\pi}{\lambda_0} \right)^2 (V) = \epsilon_{tf} \quad (8)$$

where V is given by (7). Eqn 8 will yield a value for the critical applied displacement u_a . Dividing u_a by L will then give us the failure strain $\epsilon_{\text{failure}}$.

Matrix Failure

Failure of the matrix may occur in two modes: interlaminar failure due to the interlaminar stresses, and failure within a 0° ply due to shear stresses that develop in-between 0° fibers as a result of their in-phase buckling. For interlaminar shear failure, we choose a quadratic criterion:

$$\sqrt{\left(\tau_{zy} \left(\frac{W_i}{2}, u_a \right) \right)^2 + \left(\tau_{zx} \left(\frac{W_i}{2}, u_a \right) \right)^2} = \tau_f \quad (9)$$

where τ_f is the shear failure strain of the matrix. Eqn 9 will yield a value for the critical applied displacement u_a . Dividing u_a by L will then give us the failure strain $\epsilon_{\text{failure}}$. This failure criterion is not conservative because it does not include the interlaminar normal stress σ_z which could play a role if the layup sequence is such that σ_z is positive, that is, if it tends to peel off 0° plies from their neighboring plies. For in-ply shear failure, the acting stress is τ_{xy} , given by the relation:

$$\max \{ \tau_{xy} \} = G_m \cdot \max \{ \gamma_{xy} \} = G_m \cdot \max \left\{ \left[\frac{d(v - v_0)}{dx} \right] \right\} \quad (10)$$

The failure criterion will

$$G_m \left(\frac{\pi}{\lambda_0} \right) (V - V_0) = \tau_f \quad (11)$$

Eqn 11 will yield a value for the critical applied displacement u_a . Dividing u_a by L will then give us the failure strain $\epsilon_{failure}$. We are now able to investigate analytically the failure in compression of a laminate $[\theta/-\theta/0_2/\theta/-\theta/0]_s$ as a function of the angle θ .

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Composite plates with generic layups $[\theta/-\theta/0_2/\theta/-\theta/0]_s$ were compression molded at 320 °C at 0.85 MPa for 15 min from a roll of AS4 fiber/polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) prepregs. Untabbed samples (80 mm x 12.7 mm x 1.7 mm) were diamond machined from these plates for uniaxial compression testing in a Boeing modified ASTM D695 compression fixture. Specially manufactured jigs (similar to [20]) were used to clamp the top and bottom of the specimens to prevent crushing and brooming of the ends. Bolt torque of the compression fixture was close to zero and maintained at a uniform level to allow accurate comparisons between samples (see [28]). Strain gages were mounted on both sides of each specimen in the central gage region. The chosen gage length was calculated to prevent gross Euler buckling of the specimens and allow for positioning of the strain gages. An Instron 4505 compression tester was used to obtain load/deflection curves. Tests were performed at a loading speed of 0.05 mm/min. Specimens final failure was considered to coincide with the fibers microbuckling failure strain. This was justified by the fact that fully straight samples failed catastrophically.

The failure strains for all samples as a function of the angle θ are plotted in Figure 1 together with a fourth degree polynomial fitting curve as shown. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.88, thus confirming the existence of a minimum strain around $\theta = 20^\circ$ and a maximum strain around $\theta = 60^\circ$.

Fig. 1: Curve fit of experimental data

ANALYSIS

Parameter values used for analysis are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameter values

E_f (GPa)	E_m (GPa)	G_m (GPa)	τ_f (GPa)	ν_{12}	ϵ_{tf} (m/m)	r_f (μm)	e (μm)	V_f
214	3.4	1.3	80	0.3	0.014	3.5	12.3	0.6

The interlaminar stresses were calculated using the symbolic software package "Maple V" (Release 3). The shear stresses τ_{zx} and τ_{zy} were maximum at the edges. Figure 2 shows the variation of the amplitude of these stresses at the edge at the three ($\theta/0$) interfaces. These are interfaces (2), (3) and (5), numbered from the top surface ply downward. The numbers in parentheses on Fig. 2 refer to the interface. Eqn 7 indicates that τ_{zy} promotes the microbuckling of all 0° fibers for all θ below 60° , while above 60° τ_{zy} hinders microbuckling. Figure 3 superimposes theoretical predictions on the data. Predictions are made for interface 2 in the $[\theta/-\theta/0_2/\theta/-\theta/0]_s$ layup, since interlaminar stresses are maximum there. The separate curves, numbered 1 to 5, refer to the following failure mechanisms: ① In-plane kinking (Eqn. 7), ② Out-of-plane kinking with full matrix support (Eqn. 15), ③ Out-of-plane kinking with reduced matrix support (Eqn. 16), ④ Interlaminar shear (Eqn. 9), and ⑤ In-ply matrix shear (Eqn. 11). Experimental results are indicated by cross-hairs. The predicted curve for in-plane kinking shows good agreement with experiment up to $\theta = 60^\circ$, while the out-of-plane kinking with reduced matrix support predicts the failure strains at θ greater than 60° (see paragraph below on out-of-plane microbuckling). The minimum strain at θ around 25° is a strong indication that shear stresses are the central mechanisms involved in the in-plane kinking of the edge fibers below 60° . The study of the curves showing matrix failure give some additional insight into the failure mechanisms taking place. We note that the curve predicting interlaminar failure is well above both the curve predicting fiber microbuckling and the test results. This implies that the microbuckling of the 0° fibers located at the edge, and consequently of the other 0° fibers, precedes interlaminar failure. We recall that interlaminar normal stresses σ_z were not taken into account in the failure criterion (Eqn 9), and consequently the strain for interlaminar failure predicted by our theory would in general be conservative. However the interlaminar failure strain must still be higher than the microbuckling failure strain because curves on Fig. 3 are in agreement with experiments with a similar layup [17] which showed that microbuckling was the initial failure mode.

Fig. 2: Amplitude of interlaminar shear stresses at ($\theta/0$) interfaces (2), (3) and (5)

The curve predicting shear failure of the matrix between fibers inside a 0° ply is, on the contrary, below the curve predicting fiber microbuckling and the tests results (except possibly above $\theta = 80^\circ$ for the tests). This indicates that the matrix fails in shear in between the 0° fibers before these fail in bending. This is in agreement with previous experimental results which showed matrix cracking in between 0° fibers [19]. In fact, the fiber rotation that occurs in the

Fig. 3: Theoretical curves for failure strain vs. θ in $[\theta/\theta_0/\theta_2/\theta/\theta_0]_s$

later stage of microbuckling and during kinking [7] will cause plastic yielding of the matrix. Plasticity and non-linear shear behavior were not considered in this work because the matrix was modeled as linear elastic.

Out-of-Plane Buckling

There remains a discrepancy between the in-plane kinking prediction curves and experimental results at high angles, $\theta > 60^\circ$. While the theory predicts a failure strain that keeps on increasing with θ , tests show a decrease in failure strain beyond $\theta = 60^\circ$. Study of the sign of the interlaminar stress τ_{zy} [27] shows that above $\theta = 60^\circ$ τ_{zy} and its derivative with respect to y are negative. The stress τ_{zy} thus tends to push the fibers toward the center of the specimen, and consequently to hinder the microbuckling of 0° fibers over the whole specimen width, the effect being more severe at the edges. We may therefore assume that the 0° fibers will then buckle out-of-plane, that is through the thickness (z direction). The intuitive argument behind this assumption is the following: the out-of-plane movement of the 0° fibers will cause bending of the surface ($\theta/-\theta$) plies. The resistance to the movement of the 0° fibers will thus be proportional to the bending stiffness of the surface ($\theta/-\theta$) plies. Because the bending stiffness of ($\theta/-\theta$) plies is minimum at $\theta=90^\circ$ and increases as θ decreases to 0° , the out-of-plane buckling amplitude of a 0° fiber should decrease with θ and consequently the strain to failure $\epsilon_{failure}$ should increase as θ decreases from 90° . Physically, we will also recall that out-of-plane kinking of 0° fibers had been observed in cross-ply composites [20], which is a clue that out-of-plane buckling could occur at angles θ close to 90° . In order to give a quantitative aspect to this analysis and prove that out-of-plane buckling is the favored failure mode at high angles θ , an estimation of the strain to failure due to out-of-plane buckling of the 0° fibers may be done as detailed below.

We model the surface plies ($\theta/-\theta$) as a cantilever beam of thickness ($2 \cdot h$), width W_i , and moment of inertia I_b that is subjected to a distributed lateral load q' . From the geometry of the loading and the top and bottom clamps, we consider that this beam has a length equal to g , where g is the distance between the clamps. The force q' is then [26]:

$$q'(\theta) = \frac{384 \bar{Q}_{11}(\theta) I_b}{g^4} \cdot w \quad (12)$$

Using Eqn 6 but substituting the out-of-plane amplitudes w and w_0 for v and v_0 , and replacing q by q' as given by Eqn 12, we obtain the following out-of-plane microbuckling equation:

$$E_f I \frac{d^4(w - w_0)}{dx^4} + \frac{384 \bar{Q}_{11}(\theta) I_b}{g^4} \cdot w - A_f \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f} \frac{d^2(w - w_0)}{dx^2} + \frac{A_f}{V_f} |\sigma_{0^\circ ply}| \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} = 0 \quad (13)$$

We then derive the following relation between W , u_a , and θ , in the same way Eqn 7 for $V(u_a, \theta)$ had been obtained:

$$W(u_a, \theta) = \frac{W_0}{1 - \frac{\frac{A_f}{V_f} |\sigma_{0^\circ \text{ply}}(u_a)| - \frac{384 \bar{Q}_{11}(\theta) I_b}{g^4} \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\pi}\right)^2}{E_f I \left(\frac{\pi}{\lambda_0}\right)^2 + A_f \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f}} \quad (14)$$

Now the actual distributed force q' on one 0° fiber is actually less than q' given by Eqn 12. Indeed, we may expect that several and possibly all fibers along the width will buckle out-of-plane. The distributed force q' should therefore be divided by the number of rows of fibers buckling out-of-plane. On the other hand, we have not taken into account the additional resistance to buckling that arises from the fact that the (θ/θ) surface plies are not isolated, but bound to the remaining plies by the matrix interlayers. This would contribute to an increase in the value of q' . We therefore introduce a correction coefficient C_{corr} in the expression for q' , with $0 < C_{\text{corr}} < 1$. Eqn 14 becomes then:

$$W(u_a, \theta) = \frac{W_0}{1 - \frac{\frac{A_f}{V_f} |\sigma_{0^\circ \text{ply}}(u_a)| - C_{\text{corr}} \left(\frac{384 \bar{Q}_{11}(\theta) I_b}{g^4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\pi} \right)^2}{E_f I \left(\frac{\pi}{\lambda_0} \right)^2 + A_f \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f}} \quad (15)$$

For a correction coefficient equal to 0.25, Eqn 15 yields predictions for the buckling strain which are well above experimental values in the angle range $\theta > 60^\circ$, as shown on Fig. 3. This indicates that the matrix offers actually a less than ideal support to the buckling fibers. In any case the actual support from the matrix depends on the three dimensional stress field around the fibers, which cannot reasonably be computed, as well as on possible matrix yielding and cracking. We may therefore model the reduced matrix support by introducing a coefficient of reduction C_{red} and modifying Eqn 15 as follows:

$$W(u_a, \theta) = \frac{W_0}{1 - \frac{\frac{A_f}{V_f} |\sigma_{0^\circ \text{ply}}(u_a)| - C_{\text{corr}} \left(\frac{384 \bar{Q}_{11}(\theta) I_b}{g^4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\pi} \right)^2}{E_f I \left(\frac{\pi}{\lambda_0} \right)^2 + A_f \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f} C_{\text{red}}} \quad (16)$$

Choosing C_{red} equal to 1/3 yields results in agreement with experimental values, as shown on Fig. 3.

CONCLUSIONS

The present work proposes a new theory for the prediction of compressive failure strains for multidirectional GFRP laminates. The theory (and its associated failure criterion) hinges on the in-plane microbuckling of the 0° fibers, but unlike previous attempts, it incorporates the influence of interlaminar shear stresses upon 0° fibers microbuckling. Such a modeling

approach is physically more sound as it takes into account experimental observation of critical microbuckling initiation at specimens edges. Good agreement between theoretical predictions and experimental results is obtained at low and intermediate angles (below 60°), and consequently it establishes the critical role played by interlaminar edge shear stresses in the failure process of multidirectional laminates. Modification of the theory to cover out-of-plane microbuckling of the 0° fibers reveals that out-of-plane microbuckling becomes the preferred failure mode at high angles (above 70°). The theory also predicts correctly that kinking occurs before interlaminar shear failure, and that the matrix in between the 0° fibers within a 0° ply would yield or crack before fiber failure in bending.

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